

EFFECTS OF COMBINED ENVIRONMENTAL AGENTS ON PULTRUDED GFRP COMPOSITES FOR BUILDING CONSTRUCTIONS

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1 Introduction

In several civil engineering applications, fiber reinforced polymer (FRP) composites are currently used as reinforcing rods, wraps for seismic retrofit of columns, externally bonded reinforcement for strengthening of walls, beams, and slabs, composite bridge decks, hybrid and all-composites structural systems. Their advantages are: low weight, high stiffness-to-weight and strength-to-weight ratios, ease of installation on the construction sites and potentially high overall durability. The properties of FRP composites are relatively known to scientists and engineers. Many concerns about the overall durability of these materials when exposed to severe environmental conditions are still under investigation [1].

Several environmental agents generate ageing mechanisms in these materials, but the currently available data in literature are generally limited to the effect of a single or a couple of environmental agents: low temperature, elevated temperature, moisture absorption and UV radiation.

The aim of present research is to monitor the effect of a combination of relevant environmental agents on some mechanical and aesthetical properties of GFRP materials produced with different resins. Glass fiber pultruded profiles have been exposed in a climatic chamber to a combination of elevated and sub-zero temperatures, moisture (high levels of relative humidity close to the saturation grade) and UV radiation. Three GFRP composites have been investigated: isophthalic polyester/E-glass, orthophthalic polyester/E-glass and vinylester/E-glass.

Mechanical and aesthetical performances have been collected over 24 consecutive weeks. Tensile, flexural and inter-laminar shear tests have been performed on aged specimens and un-aged materials. Moreover, change in colour and lightness has been measured during the ageing period.

The features of the materials after the artificial ageing have been compared to those of specimens exposed to natural ageing in external atmosphere of a semi-continental large city like Milan (Italy). The specimens, exposed to the natural climate, have been tested after 12 months.

2 Materials

Materials under investigation are pultruded plates produced using E-glass fibres and three different compositions of matrices, namely isophthalic polyester, orthophthalic polyester and vinylester. Heat deflection temperature (HDT) for the resins, measured by the producer, is 90°C for isophthalic polyester, 80°C for orthophthalic polyester and 105°C for vinylester.

The plates contain unidirectional rowing of 4800 tex and mat of 300 g/m². The fiber volume fraction for the three compositions is ≈60% of which ≈48% is unidirectional rowing and ≈12% is continuous mat. The plates layout is composed of two external layers of mat and one internal layer of rowing. A polyester tissue is applied on top on one side. The polyester layer represents the 0.7% of the composites weight. Total thickness of the plate is 2.85 mm. The side with the polyester tissue was exposed to the artificial UV radiation within the climatic chamber and to the sunlight during the process of natural ageing.

3 Ageing set-up

The artificial ageing refers to a period of 24 weeks (six months) equivalent to 504 cycles divided in 'cold' and 'warm' cycles. The 252 'cold' cycles had a range of temperatures $-20^{\circ}\text{C} \div +20^{\circ}\text{C}$, while for the 252 'warm' cycles was $+20^{\circ}\text{C} \div +60^{\circ}\text{C}$. The relative humidity (RH) was maintained equal to 90% for the 'cold' and to 80% for the 'warm' cycle. This setting simulates the extreme weather conditions that can be encountered in a semi-continental climate, characterized by a cold/wet winter and a hot/wet summer.

Fig. 1. Temperature and relative humidity for (a) 'cold' and (b) 'warm' cycles.

Data collected from a weather data centre in the last decade have been used to properly define the artificial ageing. Maximum temperature of 60°C in

the warm cycle was selected considering the temperature on a surface exposed to the direct sunlight during summer. Minimum temperature of -20°C was chosen considering the extreme sub-zero temperatures recorded in Milan in the last decade.

The 'cold' and 'warm' cycles have been alternated every 21 cycles (one week). Fig. 1 shows the temperature and the relative humidity diagrams for both cycles.

Specimens were maintained under the described conditions within a Binder MKF-720 climatic chamber, equipped with a set of four fluorescent UV lamps (Fig. 2). UV lamps emit on a wavelength in the range of $340\div 400\text{ nm}$ with a peak for a wavelength of 350 nm , according to the standard [2], and produce an irradiance of 40 W/m^2 on the specimen surface.

Two lamps Philips Actinic BL 40W Reflector for each layer of specimens were used. The lamps have been alternatively turned-on and off every 12 hours. Some samples have been exposed to natural ageing in the external environment of Milan. The pultruded plates of the three compositions have been placed on a dark horizontal roof, 10 m from the ground, for twelve consecutive months.

Fig. 2. The Binder MKF-720 climatic chamber used for artificial aging.

4 Mechanical tests

The influence of the aging on the main mechanical properties of GFRPs pultruded plate was investigated performing tensile, flexural and inter-laminar shear tests, both in the rowing direction (0°) and perpendicularly to it (90°).

Five specimens for traction were tested both for 0° and 90° direction, according to [3]. The strain in the load direction was measured by an extensometer MTS 634.25F-24, base length 50 mm.

Specimens for the flexural test have been prepared according to [4], both in 0° and 90° direction. The test has been conducted using a three-point loading arrangement with span of 40 mm.

The specimens for ILSS in the rowing direction were according to [5]. The short beam had supports distance of 15 mm.

5 Spectrophotometry

The atmospheric ageing could produce variation of colour and hence an aesthetical degradation. The variations of the surface colour and lightness, both for specimens after artificial and natural ageing, have been estimated using a Minolta CM-2600d spectrophotometer. The results have been expressed in terms of the CIE L*a*b system according to [6]. In this system, L* refers to the measurement of lightness, a* and b* give the measurements in the green-red and blue-yellow range, respectively.

6 Results

The influence of the aging is estimated comparing the properties of un-aged materials (month 0) with those after conditioning in the artificial environment. The mechanical and aesthetical properties have been measured after each month of artificial aging. These have been compared to those after 12 months of natural environment exposition.

6.1 Weight variation

The coupling of humidity and temperature is considered one of the main responsible of the mechanical properties degradation (see e.g. [7], [8]). The moisture uptake is considered an indication of the imparted matrix crack density and of the debonding at the interface between fibers and matrix [9].

An initial evaluation of the effects of the relative humidity and temperature within the climatic chamber was performed weighting specimens after each month of artificial aging. Weight variations was estimated as: $100 \times (m(t) - m(0)) / m(0)$, being $m(0)$ and $m(t)$ the specimen mass at the initial state and at time t [10].

The measurements in Fig. 3 show $\approx 0.1\%$ weight decrease in the first month. This initial behavior can

be explained as a loss of styrene [11]. In the second and third month, the moisture absorption generates a progressive weight increase of about 0.4%. This reflects a growth of crack density allowing water permeation. In the remaining time, the weight has an oscillation below and above 0.4%. It is highly probable that, for a longer period, the saturation rate would be close to the increment of 0.4%.

The three compositions have similar moisture absorption, even though vinylester matrix absorbs less moisture if compared to polyesters.

It must be mentioned that the present measurements represent the effect of cyclic variation of humidity and temperature while most of the results available in literature are consequence of constant environmental conditions (humidity and/or temperature).

Fig. 3. Weight variation during artificial ageing.

6.2 Mechanical tests

6.2.1 Tensile properties

Diagrams in Fig. 4 show the variation after artificial ageing of the average tensile strength and elastic modulus. Moreover, Fig. 4 presents the tensile properties after twelve months of natural aging (12N).

Tensile strength in rowing direction (0°) (Fig. 4a) shows the larger part of the reduction in the initial three months. Slight variation is in the fourth and fifth month and a further reduction in the remaining aging time. After six months, the composite with isophthalic polyester matrix has a strength loss of about 15%, orthophthalic polyester of about 10% and vinylester of about 14%. Twelve months of

natural ageing generate a decrease of strength in rowing direction lower than the artificial aging both for isophthalic polyester and vinylester ($\approx 10\%$), while for the orthophthalic polyester is about 18%. Tensile modulus in rowing direction (0°) does not vary significantly; the differences are in the range of the experimental data scatter band (Fig. 4b). An analogous behavior is observed after twelve months of natural ageing. In the rowing direction, only the tensile strength varies, mainly in the initial three months of artificial aging, and the effect is similar to that of twelve months of natural aging.

Fig. 4. Results of the tensile tests. Variation of the average strength (a,c) and of the average elastic modulus (b,d); in 0° (a,b) and 90° (c,d) direction. Bars indicate standard deviation. '12N' means 12 months of natural ageing.

The matrix dominant direction (90°) had a fast reduction of the tensile strength in the first half of the artificial aging (Fig. 4c). After six months, the reduction for composite with isophthalic polyester is about 29%, for orthophthalic is 33% and the vinylester has a degradation of 15% of the initial value. Twelve months of natural ageing do not show a significant impact on the transverse strength. The artificial ageing had an important effect on the elastic modulus in transversal direction (Fig. 4d). Both polyester matrices based composites have a considerable decrease of stiffness, close to 20% of the initial value. The glass/vinylester composite shows a slightly variable stiffness, within the

experimental scatter. This result is explained being vinylester hydrolytically more stable than polyesters [12]. The twelve months natural ageing have not relevant effect on the 90° direction elastic modulus.

6.2.2 Flexural properties

The flexural strength in rowing direction (0°) has an initial increase for the isophthalic polyester, a reduction in the second and third month of artificial ageing and then remains stable (Fig. 5a). After six months, a reduction of 15% and 11% is observed for the orthophthalic polyester and the vinylester based composites, respectively. The same trend is observed after twelve months of natural ageing with slight lower amount of strength loss (Fig. 5a).

Fig. 5. Results of the flexural tests. Average strength (a,c) and of average modulus (b,d); in 0° (a,b) and 90° (c,d) direction. Bars indicate standard deviation. '12N' means 12 months of natural ageing.

The flexural modulus in rowing direction (0°) seems to be unaffected by the aging (Fig. 5b). It shows a negative trend after twelve months of natural ageing, comparable to the artificial ageing.

The natural and artificial ageing demonstrate similar influence on the bending behavior in rowing direction.

Analogous comments arise for the bending properties in the matrix dominant direction (90°). The flexural strength decreases in the first half of the artificial ageing (Fig. 5c), even though in the first month an evident improvement is recorded. This is probably consequence of a further polymerization [13] combined with a hardening effect of the matrices [14] due to the high and low temperatures

imposed in the climate chamber. The aging does not affect the flexural modulus in 90° direction (Fig. 5d). It has a reduction below 6%, comparable to the experimental scatter band. Twelve months of natural ageing have a similar effect.

6.2.3 Inter-laminar Shear Strength

The variation of the ILSS demonstrates different behavior of the three materials (Fig. 6). The polyester based specimens increase the inter-laminar shear strength more than 10% in the first month of artificial ageing. As mentioned above this could be the effect of a further polymerization and/or hardening of the matrices. In the following five months, ILSS decreases up to a residual positive variation lower than 3%. The vinylester based composite has an initial slight improvement and a fast degradation until the third month, than the strength remains constant with a reduction close to 8%. The natural ageing produces a similar effect on orthophthalic polyester and vinylester matrices, while it generates an enhancement in the isophthalic polyester.

Fig. 6. Results of the inter-laminar shear tests. Bars indicate standard deviation. '12N' means 12 months of natural ageing.

6.3 Colour variation

A mechanism of photo-degradation produces degradation of polymeric constituents during exposure to UV light [15].

Fig. 7. (a) lightness (L*); color variation in the (b) green-red- range (a*) and (c) blue-yellow range (b*). '12N' means 12 months of natural ageing.

The lightness measurements (L^*) for each month of exposition to artificial ageing reveal small variations for all GFRP materials (Fig. 7a). The slight increase is limited to one unit for both polyester matrices, while vinylester maintains the same lightness in the six months aging. A loss of one unit of lightness (L^*) represents a visible variation for the human eye. An analogous lightness variation is observed after the natural aging in the polyester matrix composites (≈ 2 units), while the vinylester one has a reduction of 4 units.

Measurements of the colours show, during the artificial aging:

- a slight degradation of the green part and a tendency to red for the three composites (a^* , Fig. 7b);

- an increase of the yellow component (b^* , Fig. 7c).

The variation of b^* is close to 3 units for both materials with polyester matrices. The composite with vinylester matrix has a lower variation along both the red-green and blue-yellow axes.

The natural aging does not modify the green part of the colour in the polyester composites and shows the same trend of the artificial on the vinylester (Fig. 7b). On the blue-yellow scale, the natural exposition generates 5 and 10 units of increment for the polyester and vinylester composites, respectively. This reflects the strong yellowing effect induced by the environmental exposition of composites.

The UV wavelength does not cover the complete spectrum of the sunlight. This produces the discrepancies in the lightness and colour variations between natural and artificial exposition, mainly for vinylester composite.

7 Conclusions

The data detailed in this paper suggest some conclusions. The mechanical features, mainly strengths, have slight variation in the first month and faster degradation in the second and third month, than the composite materials have a slower reduction or a stabilization of the measured properties. The comparison of mechanical features and weight variation suggest some links.

1) The loss of weight in the first month, explained as a loss of styrene and further polymerization of the matrices, produces a small increase or negligible reduction of the mechanical properties.

2) In the second and third months the materials have a larger increment of weight, as consequence of the

increase of crack density. This generates a larger reduction of the strength.

3) The weight is stable in the fourth month of artificial aging, while it has an oscillation over the same value in the last two months. This behavior could be consequence of a stabilization of the cracks pattern already imparted. The counterpart in term of mechanical properties is a small reduction or invariance.

The six month combination of high temperature, freeze-thaw cycles, relative humidity and UV radiation imposed in the climatic chamber has similar effect of the twelve months natural ageing in the rowing direction. The artificial ageing accelerates the reduction of the mechanical properties in the matrix dominant direction.

It is also possible to conclude that the combination of weathering agents generates a greater influence on the mechanical performance of GFRP materials if compared to literature data obtained with the application of a single environmental agent [14].

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